

Piping and Instrumentation Diagram Analysis for Efficient Reverse Osmosis of Seawater Desalination Operations

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Abstract

The process of making seawater fresh and useable by eliminating salt and contaminants is known as desalination. It supplies pure water for industrial, agricultural, and drinking uses. In regions with limited freshwater supplies, this approach is particularly helpful. The design and creation of a comprehensive Process and Instrumentation (P&I) diagram for a PLC-based seawater desalination system is the main goal of this project. Using sophisticated management and monitoring via PLC automation, the system is designed to transform saltwater into drinkable fresh water. Seawater intake starts the process, which is then followed by other treatment steps like filtration, desalination, and purification. A constant water quality monitoring mechanism is incorporated into the system to ensure quality. The PLC logic automatically reroutes the output water back into the reprocessing cycle for additional treatment if it does not meet the required criteria during desalination. To reduce the risk of contamination, water is rejected if, even after reprocessing, it still does not reach the necessary purity. This automated decision-making reduces the need for human involvement while guaranteeing excellent process reliability. High-quality drinkable water that satisfies safety regulations is the end result. The treated water can also be used for home, agricultural, or industrial purposes, depending on the purity levels attained. Thus, the suggested PLC-controlled desalination system meets the demand for fresh water from seawater resources worldwide while guaranteeing sustainability, efficiency, and dependability.

Keywords: P&I diagram, Seawater Desalination, PLC, and Reverse Osmosis.

1. Introduction

High-quality water is essential for technological operations, necessitating stringent control parameters to prevent the adverse effects of unintended acidity. A well-integrated control system comprising sensors, actuators, and control elements enables automation of these processes [1]. Meanwhile, the vast oceans contain undrinkable water, presenting a serious challenge for future generations. Desalination has become the most widely adopted method for converting seawater into fresh water [2]. Waterborne infections, particularly fluorosis, affect approximately 40 million people annually, with children being the most vulnerable. In response, the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC) is actively developing desalination and water purification technologies to meet the growing demand for potable water [3]. This study offers a comprehensive review of recent advancements in reverse osmosis (RO) desalination plants, with particular focus on solar-powered systems that aim to reduce energy consumption through natural, organic cycles [4]. As freshwater resources become increasingly scarce and population growth continues, developing energy-efficient and cost-effective desalination technologies has become critical. In this regard, RO technology stands out as the most viable solution [5]. A key metric in desalination is plant recovery, which refers to the percentage of seawater converted into fresh water. Typically, seawater reverse osmosis (SWRO) units achieve a recovery rate of 45%–55% [6-8]. To support efficient water treatment processes, a SCADA control panel has been developed for wastewater management and monitoring. This system connects

(Programmable Logic Controller) for seamless control [9]. Utilizing Siemens Ltd.'s PLC along with KINGVIEW6.53 software, the system has significantly enhanced the operational efficiency and management of sewage treatment facilities [10]. PLCs offer numerous benefits, including the reduction of labor-intensive, repetitive, and hazardous tasks. Their increasing adoption contributes to process optimization, improved productivity, profitability, and attractive investment opportunities key aspects of Industry 4.0 [11-13]. In particular, the implementation of radar sensors for liquid level control in tanks provides scalability and flexibility, allowing integration with broader monitoring systems in plants, ships, and other infrastructure [14]. The use of PLC and SCADA in sewage water treatment enables the reuse of purified water for domestic and agricultural applications. This approach addresses the limitations of traditional float sensors, reduces costs, and mitigates disruptions caused by vibrations [15-18]. Furthermore, by incorporating Internet of Things (IoT) capabilities, the system supports remote monitoring, historical data logging, and real-time alerts enhancing operational efficiency, enabling preventive maintenance, and facilitating informed decision-making [19-20]. The present work is organized into separate chapters, starting with a thorough analysis of the entire work of literature that emphasizes the contributions of numerous scholars. After that, an in-depth description of the suggested approach is given, and finally, the experimental studies and findings are presented.

2. Literature Review

In 1988, a researcher conducted design and simulation experiments for large-scale desalination plants, evaluating convergence criteria such as stability, iteration count, computing time, and sensitivity to initial conditions. The study also critically analyzed the model's approximation assumptions, highlighting its potential applicability in real-world scenarios [21]. However, beyond computational modeling, subsequent research focused on the financial and operational aspects of decentralized desalination systems. These studies revealed that, although the initial costs for hardware and software are higher compared to centralized systems, operational and maintenance expenses could be reduced by up to 75% due to lower manpower requirements. This demonstrates that decentralized models not only improve efficiency but also provide a cost-effective approach for reverse osmosis desalination plants [22]. Furthermore, investigations into integrated systems comprising pumps, membrane racks, and isobaric energy recovery devices analyzed how these components influence flushing processes, respond to varying membrane conditions, and adapt to changes in water quality [23]. In addition, solar-powered desalination models have been developed, particularly for regions such as Manaure, La Guajira, Colombia, with an emphasis on integrating renewable energy sources. These models aim to reduce energy consumption, lower overall operational costs, and mitigate the environmental and health impacts typically associated with conventional desalination processes [24, 25]. Moreover, significant attention has been given to the role of monitoring and automation in improving system efficiency. Sensor-integrated circuits coupled with HTML dashboards have enabled real-time monitoring of critical parameters such as temperature, humidity, and water levels, providing valuable insights for design optimization and supporting water autonomy initiatives [26, 27]. In addition, hybrid desalination systems that combine solar energy with IoT and sensor networks allow continuous real-time performance and water quality monitoring. These systems can promptly detect operational issues, facilitating timely corrective actions and ensuring a sustainable supply of freshwater [28]. The use of AI-based methods has further enhanced monitoring capabilities. For instance, Ada-Boost was found to outperform other machine learning models in predicting the presence of *E. coli* in water, with turbidity, nitrates, conductivity, pH, chloride, and chlorophyll identified as the most informative parameters for accurate forecasting [29]. Similarly, IoT-enabled water monitoring systems, incorporating Arduino controllers, PLCs, and Bluetooth modules, have been implemented to automate data collection and transmission to mobile devices, proving their utility in both drinking water treatment and wastewater

management [30]. In terms of remote monitoring and control, cloud-based architectures and Node-RED servers have enabled automated responses whenever water quality parameters exceed predefined thresholds. This allows pumps and other connected devices to operate remotely, ensuring timely intervention and minimizing manual oversight [31, 32]. Furthermore, sensor-to-cloud systems transmit pH, turbidity, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and temperature readings through microcontrollers and Raspberry Pi controllers to browser-based applications, providing accessible, real-time data visualization [33]. These technologies have also been adapted for aquaculture, where wireless sensor systems monitor water quality parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, water level, and sensor health, with data transmitted to mobile devices for immediate action by farm managers [34]. To further improve operational efficiency, predictive maintenance, and resource optimization, Deep Belief Networks (DBNs) have been integrated with IoT–SCADA architectures. This integration employs Complex Event Processing (CEP) to analyze massive streams of real-time sensor data, evaluate treatment effectiveness, and ensure chemical emissions remain within permissible limits [35]. Finally, experimental studies utilizing Arduino-based sensors for conductivity, temperature, pH, turbidity, and total dissolved solids (TDS) have validated water quality models for running water. These experiments demonstrated that the studied water sources met established standards, confirming the effectiveness of the proposed monitoring and control strategies [36–38].

3. Proposed Work

The suggested system is a PLC-based automation approach for saltwater desalination that provides efficient, consistent, and continuous production of potable water. The simple block diagram of RO desalination process is shown in the Figure 1.1. The technique combines mechanical filtration, reverse osmosis (RO), and programmable logic control (PLC) to improve monitoring and decision-making. Seawater inflow from the source starts the desalination process. To get rid of big pollutants and suspended solids, the water is pre-treated using filtering and sedimentation.

Fig. 1.1 Block Diagram of PLC-based RO Desalination System

The water is subsequently forced into the RO membrane unit by a high-pressure pump, where pollutants and dissolved salts are removed. The concentrated brine is disposed of safely, and the pure freshwater is gathered in a storage tank. To track parameters including flow rate, pressure, turbidity, total dissolved solids (TDS), and pH in real time, a PLC controller is included into the system. The PLC guarantees automatic fault diagnosis, pump control, and valve operation based on sensor inputs. Operational reliability is increased and human error is decreased by this automation.

3.1 Seawater Intake & Pretreatment feed

Water treatment systems remove macroscopic debris like leaves and plastics using trash racks and coarse screening to prevent clogging and protect downstream equipment. Bar spacing varies between 10 and 50 mm, depending on debris volume. Intake pumps deliver seawater to the pretreatment phase, with protective screens and a Net Positive Suction Head margin to prevent cavitations. Variable Frequency Drive (VFD) provides accurate flow regulation and soft-start functionality. Chemical dosing at the intake can manage bio-fouling and scaling, especially in high bio-load situations. Early introduction of anti-scale or anti-bio-fouling chemicals maintains the effectiveness of the seawater treatment process and protects downstream equipment.

3.2 Primary Pretreatment

Flocculation and coagulation are methods used to combine suspended particles into larger flocs, improving particle removal during filtration or sedimentation. Water is typically held in a flocculator for a few minutes to ensure proper contact. Sedimentation or clarification removes flocs and reduces turbidity and silt. The system is designed with an appropriate overflow rate to achieve the target turbidity, typically less than 5 NTU, before filtration. Multimedia filtration, typically with layers of sand and anthracite, removes suspended solids from water. These filters can be backwashed to restore functionality. Cartridge polishing filters, with a rating of 1-5 μm , remove fine particulates from water, providing protection for reverse osmosis membranes, preventing fouling and maintaining system efficiency.

3.3 High-Pressure Pumping and RO Feed Conditioning

Depending on the total dissolved solids (TDS), the high-pressure pump (HP pump) raises the water pressure to the operating level needed for reverse osmosis, which is normally 40–70 bar for saltwater. For safety and monitoring, the system should have a pressure transducer and a pressure relief valve. It is advised to use variable frequency drive (VFD) control to maximize energy efficiency and enable accurate pump operation adjustment. To avoid scale formation on RO membranes, pH modification and anti-scalant dosage are essential. In order to prevent the precipitation of salts like CaCO_3 and BaSO_4 , anti-scalant chemicals are usually dosed using a 4–20 mA regulated pump. The dosage is based on the temperature and TDS of the feed water. When necessary, acid dosage may be used to reduce the pH in order to manage particular scaling tendencies. Moreover, sodium bi-sulfite must be used to eliminate any chlorine that may have been in the feed water in order to shield the polyamide membranes from oxidative degradation.

3.4 Reverse Osmosis (RO) Stage

Pressure vessels include reverse osmosis (RO) membrane elements, usually of the spiral-wound variety, which are used to treat high-salinity seawater. Depending on the system design and feed-water quality, these membranes can be set up in single-stage or multi-stage configurations to achieve increased water recovery. Through specialized plumbing, permeate from the RO system is gathered and sent to the permeate tank. The permeate line is equipped with conductivity or TDS sensors to continuously check the water quality and make sure it satisfies the necessary requirements. The concentrate, or brine, from the RO system is returned to the brine line and disposed of using methods such as diffusers, deep-well injection, evaporation ponds, or brine concentrators for zero liquid discharge (ZLD) systems. A flow meter and a dump valve are typically provided to monitor and control the brine flow, ensuring safe and efficient disposal.

3.5 Post-treatment & Storage

Polishing processes, if required, include re-mineralization and disinfection using UV or chlorine to ensure the water meets potable quality standards. The treated water is stored in a tank equipped with level control and overflow protection to maintain safe and reliable operation.

3.6 PLC, HMI, SCADA & Data logging

The PLC communicates with a variety of sensors, including those for pressure, flow, conductivity, pH, level, and turbidity, as well as actuators like pumps, valves, and dosing pumps. An HMI allows operators to input data and view trends in real time, whereas SCADA or RTU systems allow for remote monitoring, control, and data logging for comprehensive process management.

4. Process and Instrumentation (P&I) diagram

In order to eliminate suspended solids and avoid scaling or fouling, the system starts with the intake of raw saltwater through feed pumps and pretreatment units that include sand filters and chemical dosing. After stabilizing the seawater in a feed tank, high-pressure pumps push it through reverse osmosis (RO) membranes to remove salt. Continuous monitoring and process optimization are ensured by instrumentation components like control valves, flow meters, and pressure gauges are shown in the Figure 1.2. Fresh water is supplied via the permeate stream, and the reject brine is securely released. For the purpose of to guarantee effective desalination operation, this design emphasizes the integration of mechanical, electrical, and control components. The detailed specifications of all the processes are presented in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Technical Specifications of P & I diagram

Tags	Function	Sensor Type / Actuator	Signal to PLC
FI-101	Feed flow (intake)	Electromagnetic / turbine flow meter	4–20 mA
PSH-101 / PSL-101	Suction pressure high/low	Pressure transducer	Digital alarm / 4–20 mA
PT-201	RO feed pressure	Pressure transducer (0–70 bar)	4–20 Ma
FT-202	Permeate flow	Flow meter (low flow)	4–20 mA
CT-301	Conductivity (permeate)	Conductivity sensor/TDS	4–20 mA or RS485
LT-401	Freshwater tank level	Ultrasonic / differential pressure	4–20 mA / digital
TUR-501	Turbidity (pretreatment outlet)	Nephelometric sensor	4–20 mA
D-601, D-602	Chemical dosing pumps	Metering pumps (anti-scalant / acid)	Digital output / analog Control
V-701	Reject valve (brine)	Motorised valve or solenoid	DO / analog (position)
MTR-801	HP Pump Motor	Motor starter + VFD	Digital + analog (VFD speed 4–20 mA or 0–10 V)

4.1 Start-up & Interlocks

1. Preconditions

- Suction pressure is greater than the PSL set point and the intake pump is ready.
- All necessary valves (auto-close interlocks) are in the start positions.
- The minimum level in chemical dosing tanks is digitally input.

2. Start sequence

- Intake pump (soft-start via VFD) is started.

Fig. 1.2 Illustrates the seawater reverse osmosis desalination process, showing feed pretreatment, high-pressure pumping, RO membrane separation, and instrumentation for monitoring permeate and reject streams.

- To reach the RO feed pressure set point (proportional ramp), initiate the HP Pump ramp via VFD when feed flow is greater than the minimum and turbidity is less than the set point.
- After the pressure stabilizes, open the feed valves to the RO.

3. Automatic stabilization

- Set the plant to RUN mode after the permeate flow stabilizes and the permeate conductivity falls below the conduct set point.

4. Shutdown & safety:

- The PLC trips the HP pump and sounds an alarm in the event of high pressure, low suction, high motor current or high turbidity; it also initiates an automatic safe shutdown sequence (close feed, stop pumps).

4.2 Control loops

1. RO Feed Pressure Control (PID)

- PT-201 (feed pressure) was measured.
- Actuator: HP Pump (4–20 mA or digital set point) using VFD speed reference
- Goal: Use as little energy as possible while maintaining the pressure needed to achieve recovery.
- Tuning: use step tests to make adjustments after starting with a conservative PID (P small); include output limitations and anti-windup.

2. Permeate Conductivity Control

- CT-301 (permeate conductivity) was measured.
- Actuator: If conductivity exceeds the set point, start the flush or CIP or modifies the recovery or concentrate valve.
- Logic: Reduce recovery or initiate membrane flushing if conductivity exceeds the alert stage.

3. Filter Backwash Control

- Measured: timer and ΔP across the filter (differential pressure)
- Actuator: Backwash pump and valve
- Rule: PLC records the number of backwashes; auto-backwash when $\Delta P >$ threshold OR schedule period.

4. Dosing Control (anti-scalant & acid)

- Temperature and feed conductivity were measured in order to calculate the scaling index.
- Actuator: Enable/Dose pump frequency
- Approach: Feedback adjustments based on trends in permeate conductivity, with feed-forward dosing proportionate to feed flow (e.g., dosing rate = $k \times$ feed flow).

5. RO membrane operation

- Operating window: Depending on the membrane type and feed salinity, seawater RO normally runs between 40 and 70 bar. Select a polyamide thin-film composite membrane that is rated for seawater.

- Recovery: 30–50% is the average single-stage seawater RO recovery; a higher recovery raises the risk of scaling. Designs that are brackish-specific or multi-stage vary.

6. Fouling indicators

- Membrane fouling or a decrease in permeates flux under constant pressure.
- A sharp rise in feed pressure or differential pressure at constant flow.
- Increase in permeate conductivity (membrane compaction or breach).

7. CIP procedure

- Separate the RO permeate and feed lines.
- Re-circulate the cleaning solution (alkaline/NaOCl for bio-fouling, acid for scaling) according to the membrane vendor's suggested concentration and contact duration.
- Verify flux recovery and permeate conductivity after a thorough rinse.

5. Performance metrics

❖ Salt rejection (%)

$$\text{Salt rejection} = \left(1 - \frac{C_p}{C_f}\right) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

where C_f = Feed Concentration (TDS or conductivity) and C_p = Permeate Concentration.

❖ Recovery ratio (%)

$$\text{Recovery} = \frac{Q_p}{Q_f} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where Q_p = Permeate flow, and Q_f = Feed flow.

❖ Specific Energy Consumption (SEC)

$$\text{SEC}(kWh/m^3) = \frac{P_{pump} \times Q_f}{\eta_{pump} \times Q_p \times 3600} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

where P_{pump} in Watts, η_{pump} is pump efficiency and factor 3600 converts J to Wh.

❖ Permeate flux (LMH)

$$\text{Flux}(L/m^2) = \frac{Q_p \times 1000}{A_{membrane} \times 3600} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

where $A_{membrane}$ is membrane active area (m^2).

6. Experimental Result

The Experimental results are shown below. The experimental results were achieved by methodically assessing the system performance based on the planned tests. The impact of feed TDS on salt rejection and

permeate quality made it abundantly evident that raising feed salinity required greater feed pressures while simultaneously increasing permeate conductivity and decreasing rejection efficiency. The recovery versus pressure experiments verified that recovery could only be enhanced up to a certain point, after which concentration polarization and osmotic pressure led to abrupt pressure spikes and a decline in the quality of the product water. CIP scheduling is required, as evidenced by the study comparing salt rejection to feed TDS, which confirmed that rejection decreased with increasing feed concentrations and over extended operation. Maintaining operating within membrane design limits is crucial, as evidenced by the permeate flow versus pressure findings, which originally showed a linear increase in flux with trans-membrane pressure before compaction at higher pressures. PLC-based sequential start-up and feed forward adjustments successfully decreased overshoot and stabilized permeate quality more quickly than manual operation, according to the conductivity versus time tests conducted under transient conditions. Ultimately, CIP was successful in restoring baseline performance, and the pressure drop versus time study verified progressive fouling under continuous operation with an accelerated rise under pretreatment disruptions. Together, these findings confirm that the seawater desalination process achieved stable operation, consistent water quality, lower energy consumption, and efficient scheduling of preventive maintenance by combining the P&ID configuration with PLC-based automated control strategies. This ensured dependable and effective system performance.

6.1 Influence of feed TDS

The change in specific energy consumption with feed TDS is shown in Figure 1.3. The findings show that the specific energy consumption grows continuously as the feed TDS increases. Since there is less osmotic pressure and less driving power required at lower salinity levels (<10,000 ppm), the energy need is comparatively low, 1.0–1.2 kWh/m³.

Fig. 1.3 illustrates the variation of specific energy consumption (SEC) with feed water salinity

The osmotic pressure rises with rising TDS, necessitating higher applied pressure, which enhances energy consumption. The energy consumption rises more noticeably between 10,000 and 30,000 ppm, approaching 1.9 kWh/m³. Significant energy penalties at severe salinity are indicated by the energy usage exceeding 2.2 kWh/m³ at very high TDS levels (>40,000 ppm). This pattern emphasizes how higher TDS input water necessitates more energy for operation, which affects system cost and efficiency. Therefore, in order to

minimize feed salinity and maximize energy use in desalination systems, pretreatment or blending techniques might be crucial.

6.2 Recovery vs. Pressure

The system recovery (%) during starting and stabilization is shown in Figure 1.4. Because of the early membrane wetting and system modifications, recovery is initially somewhat low, at about 40%. As the system overcomes initial resistance and stabilizes flow conditions, recovery increases significantly within the first hour, reaching about 55%. The recovery increases gradually between 1 and 4 hours, reaching a peak of roughly 65%. The system has achieved a stable working condition with few recovery variations when the curve flattens out after four hours.

Fig. 1.4 The recovery percentage of the RO system is shown over time during startup and stabilization.

The system appears to maintain equilibrium with relatively small adjustments, based on the slight deviations that were noticed between 4 and 8 hours. This result demonstrates that a brief stabilizing period is necessary for the membrane system to achieve reliable operation. Overall, the findings show how crucial it is to provide desalination systems enough beginning time in order to guarantee steady recovery levels and dependable operation.

6.3 Salt Rejection vs. TDS

Figure 1.5 illustrates the influence of feed TDS on salt rejection. At ~1,000 ppm feed TDS, rejection was ~98%, but at ~45,000 ppm, it reduced to ~95.8%. This amounts to a loss of ~2.2% over the tested range, or around 0.5% decrease for every 10,000 ppm rise in feed TDS. The decrease in rejection efficiency is mostly due to increased osmotic pressure at higher salinities, which reduces the effective driving force for water transport and allows more salt to flow through the membrane. From a performance aspect, the membrane exhibits significant rejection (>95%) even at saltwater salinities, although the steady reduction suggests limitations under high-TDS operation. Practically, this tendency suggests that greater operating pressures, pretreatment, or multi-stage RO systems may be necessary to maintain both flux and salt rejection in high-salinity applications.

Fig. 1.5 shows the salt rejection efficiency of the RO membranes at different feed TDS levels.

6.4 Permeate Flow vs. Pressure

The change in permeate flow rate with applied pressure is depicted in Figure 1.6. As the applied pressure overcomes the osmotic barrier, the permeate flow rate increases quickly at lower pressures (10–20 bar), reaching roughly 60 L/h. The flow continues to climb in the mid-range (20–50 bar), but more slowly, suggesting the impact of concentration polarization and internal resistance.

Fig. 1.6 The relationship between applied feed pressure and permeate flow rate is presented.

The rise is modest at higher pressures (>50 bar), with the flow rate approaching 155 L/h at 70 bar. This pattern demonstrates that although increased pressure improves water flow, limiting variables like osmotic back pressure and membrane compaction cause efficiency to decline at higher pressures. Therefore, to achieve optimal efficiency with reduced energy usage, an ideal pressure range is required.

6.6 Conductivity vs. Time

The graphical representation shows the over the course of the 8-hour operation, the permeate conductivity showed a declining trend, beginning at around 820 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and stabilizing at about 500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ as given in the Figure 1.7. The initial sharp drop suggests that ions were effectively removed in the early phases of the process, most likely as a result of excellent membrane performance and little fouling. Conductivity variations between 2 and 6 hours point to moderate fouling events or sporadic modifications in membrane selectivity.

Fig. 1.7 The variation in permeate water conductivity over time

The system achieves a quasi-steady state with constant permeate quality when the conductivity stabilizes after six hours. These findings show that the membrane retains its efficacy with little degradation in ion rejection during prolonged use. While pointing out small operational variances that can profit from recurring inspection or cleaning, the pattern generally validates the system's capacity for continuous purification.

6.7 Pressure Drop vs. Time

The pressure drop across a membrane after 180 days of continuous operation is depicted in the graph. There is a general upward tendency, with sporadic variations suggesting fouling and partial recovery cycles, which could be brought on by cleaning or operational changes. Within 25 days, the pressure decrease first increases from about 1.0 bar to 1.7 bar, then experiences many peaks and troughs as shown in the Figure 1.8. The constant rise in every fall points to the gradual re-accumulation of foulants. The pressure decrease reaches over 3.5 bar at the end of the session, indicating severe membrane fouling. In order to preserve membrane performance and increase operational life, this approach emphasizes the necessity of optimal cleaning procedures and monitoring techniques.

Fig. 1.8 Graph shows the pressure drop across the membrane over an extended operating period.

Conclusion

This work presents a comprehensive PLC-based seawater desalination system with an integrated Process and Instrumentation (P&I) design aimed at addressing global freshwater scarcity. By combining advanced automation with continuous water quality monitoring, the system ensures reliable production of safe and high-quality water while minimizing human intervention. The automatic reprocessing and rejection mechanisms enhance efficiency, maintain strict purity standards, and reduce the risk of contamination. Furthermore, the adaptability of the treated water for domestic, industrial, and agricultural purposes highlights the system's versatility. Overall, the proposed PLC-controlled desalination approach demonstrates a sustainable, efficient, and dependable solution for transforming seawater into a valuable freshwater resource, contributing significantly to future water security.

Future Work

Future developments of this system can focus on integrating advanced sensors and IoT-based monitoring for real-time data acquisition and remote supervision. Machine learning algorithms can be employed to predict water quality variations and optimize desalination parameters automatically, thereby improving efficiency. The incorporation of renewable energy sources, such as solar or wind power, can further enhance sustainability and reduce operational costs. Additionally, expanding the system design for large-scale community applications and integrating smart storage and distribution networks will increase its practical value. Research can also be directed toward developing hybrid desalination methods to improve energy efficiency and achieve higher recovery rates.

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